

Efficient visualization of the geometric information of CityGML: Application for the documentation of built heritage

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Abstract. CityGML is a standard data model for the representation, storage and exchange of 3D city models issued by the OGC (Open Geospatial Consortium). CityGML represents a very attractive solution that combines 3D information and semantic information in a single data model. The efficient visualization of the geometric information contained in the CityGML data model is still an open challenge. A survey of the state of the art shows that current approaches have to be improved. In this paper we introduce a new approach for efficient web visualization of CityGML without plugins based on the use of X3D and web services. The approach has been evaluated with an implementation applied to built heritage at urban scale based on an extended CityGML model.

Keywords: CityGML, 3D visualization, built heritage, 3D visualization on the Web, Web Services

1 Introduction

A georeferenced virtual 3D model represents an increasingly accepted solution for storing and displaying information at urban scale. CityGML represents a very attractive solution that combines 3D information and semantic information in a single data model.

The efficient display of the geometric information in CityGML is still a big technological challenge. Stakeholders involved in process around city models demand rapid access to information anywhere at anytime. The visualization of CityGML geometry is a critical issue because there is not an appropriate/efficient format for visualization since the file size (around hundreds of megabytes), the structure of the data model (XML-based) and the geometry representation (in GML) are not designed taking in mind the exchange of information in the web.

The goal of this paper is to introduce the key technologies and open standards needed to implement a solution for efficient visualization of geometric information of CityGML in the Web 3D framework. In order to achieve this goal some steps have to

be performed. Firstly, the CityGML file is stored in a relational database to be able to retrieve and manage the information efficiently. Then, the information is exported based on the required level of detail to enable a progressive visualization of different pieces. For this, several requests are made to our custom implementation of the W3DS (Web 3D Service) so the geometric information is accessible via web. Finally, X3D file is visualized in a web browser without plugins by means of the X3DOM framework which has been adapted to our needs.

The rest of this paper is decomposed in the following sections. Section 2 makes a review of the state of the art. Section 3 presents a technological review about standards and technologies for 3D visualization on the Web. Section 4 briefly describes CityGML. Section 5 covers the details about the implementation of our approach. Finally, section 6 summarizes the conclusions extracted from our work.

2 State of the art

CityGML, issued by the OGC, is an open standard for store and exchange virtual 3D city models [1] and is an application schema for version 3.1.1 of GML. GML [2] is an extensible international standard for spatial data exchange issued also by the OGC and ISO TC211.

The aim of the development of CityGML is to reach a common definition of basic entities, attributes and relationships of a 3D city model. CityGML defines the classes of objects in city models which have been identified as necessary or relevant in many applications in different areas. CityGML also includes different LoDs (Levels of Detail) to join concepts from the scale of a city or district to a building, joining GIS (Geographic information system) and BIM (Building information modelling) concepts in a single data model.

The visualization of CityGML is a critical issue as it is denoted by the number of publications. The main author of CityGML, T.H. Kolbe, said [3] that "CityGML is not optimized with respect to efficient visualization" [4], "It is not a good idea to render the 3D scenes directly from the CityGML files". Several formats are available to represent CityGML geometry such as VRML/X3D, SketchUp, 3DMax and KML. CityGML requires more bytes to represent the same geometry [5]. The agreement between the OGC and Web3D to use X3D with OGC standards for improving location-based 3D visualization means a significant advance [6]. As a consequence, several research groups are studying how to adapt X3D for CityGML.

There exist several approaches in the literature to tackle 3D visualization of CityGML. The first approach is to visualize CityGML files in desktop viewers such as Aristoteles [7] or FZKViewer. Another approach is to develop specific viewers combining the citygml4j library and a low level graphics library like OpenGL [8]. The main drawback of this approach is that GML is not efficient for visualization.

Another approach consists of exporting the geometry of the CityGML object to a more efficient file format, like X3D, where the export has to be done offline because a lot of time is needed to export an entire city model [4]. Even when the export process is finished, specific tools or plugins are needed to visualize X3D files.

The natural evolution of this approach is the visualization of parts of the CityGML model selected using bounding boxes such that the export can be done online. The retrieval of these virtual city objects is performed using the W3DS which is a standard web service that returns the geometry in an output format such as KML, VRML or X3D. In [9] CityGML file is requested to a W3DS that returns VRML file which is visualized using the XNavigator viewer [10]. This approach makes still necessary the use of specific tools or plugins to visualize the X3D files.

In order to visualize the geometry of CityGML files directly on a web browser without using plugins, some approaches visualize pre-rendered images from different viewpoints in the server side. For this purpose, [11] shows a review of different client/server configurations where a thin client combined with the Web Perspective View Service (WPVS) were finally chosen. They developed a graphical interface to visualize geographic data in a browser by requesting images to a WPVS for the viewpoint selected by the user. A comparison between the advantages/disadvantages of WPVS against W3DS was done in [12], showing an improvement of the solution introduced in [13] where a pre-generated set of images from different viewpoints was stored and then visualized in a web browser. The main drawback of both approaches is that images do not allow navigating the model because the views are fixed. Still, depending on the user's needs it might be a sufficient solution.

Another approach for 3D visualization on web applications without plugins is explained in [4]. The Xj3D library is used in desktop visualization while the CityGML content is exported to X3D and visualized in a web browser using the X3DOM framework. The main advantage is the interoperability of the visualization but the main drawback is that the whole model needs to be exported to visualize it.

In this paper we propose a solution which combines the efficiency of representation of the geometry through X3D with the flexibility of using web services (W3DS) without requiring plugins for the visualization in a web browser.

3 Technological review

3.1 3D representation standards

As previously explained, it is not efficient to visualize 3D content directly from CityGML. In this section we will analyse different 3D standards to which export the geometry and the appearance of CityGML.

The implementation of CityGML in XML facilitates the transformation into other 3D representation standards. CityGML is based on GML, which is aimed to exchange spatial data. The most relevant open formats which can interoperate with CityGML are KML, X3D, VRML and Collada. KML is another OGC standard, focused on providing structures to represent multimedia content associated with a 3D model. KML is also the standard format for data exchange adopted by the popular application Google Earth. It has a similar structure to GML and allows attaching COLLADA models. COLLADA was designed to facilitate sharing and reuse of 3D content between different tools and content creators. VRML describe interactive three-

dimensional objects and worlds; while the purpose of X3D, its successor, is the creation and transmission of 3D content between web applications.

X3D [14] is an open standard to represent and communicate 3D scenes and objects based on XML. It is an ISO standard to store, access and play 3D content in real time over the Internet. Its main advantages are the simplicity and the possibilities to import/export from/to X3D from most known 3D representation standards.

There are also other 3D representation technologies like O3D [15] or Universal 3D [16]. The disadvantages of these standards are that they are designed only for certain tools and they are not international standards supported by different communities.

Fig. 1 presents a comparison between different 3D representation standards. It also details what features each standard supports. These features have to be analyzed to choose a standard depending on the application too. Fig. 1 shows that CityGML supports all the features and that X3D supports most of CityGML features such as geometry, textures, levels of detail and georeferencing.

In summary, we can say that KML and Collada are designed for 3D world browsers, so the export from CityGML is more limited. X3D has a geospatial component [18] and represents different levels of detail [19] which are nearer to the GIS philosophy of CityGML. Thus, X3D is the best option to represent 3D models on the Web since it is designed to be compatible with HTML and sent across the network. However, because of X3D was designed to represent geometry, CityGML semantics are lost in this conversion.

	DXF	SHP	VRML	X3D	KML	Collada	IFC	CityGML	3D PDF
Geometry	++	+	++	++	+	++	++	+	++
Topology	-	-	0	0	-	+	+	+	-
Texture	-	0	++	++	0	++	-	+	+
LOD	-	-	+	+	-	-	-	+	-
Objects	0	+	+	+	-	-	+	+	+
Semantic	+	+	0	0	0	0	++	++	+
Attributes	-	+	0	0	0	-	+	+	+
XML based	-	-	-	+	-	-	+	+	-
Web	-	-	+	++	++	+	-	+	0
Georef.	+	+	-	+	+	-	-	+	+
Acceptance	++	++	++	0	++	+	0	+	++

- not supported; 0 basic; + supported; ++ extended

Figure 1: Comparison between different 3D exchange standards [17]

3.2 Web 3D visualization

Plugins have been the predominant way of visualizing 3D content on the Web in recent years. However they have some clear disadvantages. On the one hand the user has to install the plugin, with the distrust that means and they can have security or incompatibility problems. On the other hand, the developer has to learn how to work with the plugin to develop applications. As it is said in [20], "these plugins include their own runtime-systems which control all the visualization, interaction, communication and distribution issues internally".

Until recently, 3D graphics on the Web was visualized using APIs such as Flash, O3D, VRML or X3D, but always using a specific browser and installing plugins. Currently, WebGL allows the integrations of 3D contents in the browser without plugins or additional software.

WebGL [21] is a Javascript API for rendering interactive 3D graphics on any compatible browser without plugins by binding JavaScript with OpenGL ES [4]. It has been developed by the WebGL Working Group. Currently, some of the browsers supporting WebGL are: Mozilla Firefox (desktop and mobile), Google Chrome, Safari and Opera (desktop and mobile). Some smartphones are: Nokia N900, BlackBerry playbook, Sony Ericsson Xperia. WebGL renders the 3D content in the new HTML5 canvas element [23]. Its main drawback is that WebGL is a low level API so several frameworks have been developed in order to simplify application development such as the X3DOM framework.

X3DOM is an experimental, WebGL-based, open source framework to support the discussion between W3C and Web3D communities on how to integrate the HTML5 specification and 3D content [25]. The aim of X3DOM, as said in [20], "is to ease the integration of X3D in modern web applications by directly mapping and synchronizing live DOM elements to an X3D scene mode". However, until now all browsers do not support X3DOM; only Google Chrome, Firefox and Safari support it natively and Internet Explorer using Flash. Furthermore, X3DOM does not implement all features which are traditionally found in a 3D graphic engine.

4 CityGML

The aim of CityGML is to store and exchange virtual 3D city models which are decomposed thematically into a core and other thematic modules. The core module covers the basic concepts in the background of a CityGML model. The other modules cover specific subject areas within the 3D virtual city model, such as appearance, topography, vegetation, city furniture, buildings, land use, transportation, etc.

CityGML defines five LoD to represent concepts from the scale of city or district to a building. Thus, the same object can be represented in different LoD simultaneously which allows to analyse and visualize the same object with different degrees of resolution. Fig. 2 shows the five LoDs defined by CityGML. LoD0 represents the digital terrain model in two dimensions and a half. LoD1 is the block model of buildings using prisms with flat roofs. LoD2 differentiates roof structures and thematically differentiated boundary surfaces. LoD3 denotes architectural models

detailing walls, roofs, balconies, etc. LoD4 completes LoD3 with interior structures such as rooms, doors, stairs and furniture. However, these LoDs are not necessarily valid for all projects.

The standard also enables a mechanism to allow extending CityGML semantics taking into account the different requirements of CityGML based applications. Thus, developers are encouraged to design their own extensions in order to include some required concepts and properties which are not reflected in basic CityGML. These extensions are called ADE (Application Domain Extension).

One of the main features of CityGML is the interoperability. Generated models can be easily reused in other standard and applications. We have analyzed multiple tools, technologies and standards to visualize, edit, parse, store, import/export, etc. CityGML files (see Fig. 3).

Figure 2: Different Levels of Detail defined by CityGML [1]

Figure 3: Tools, technologies and standards around CityGML [26]

5 Implementation

This section presents the implementation of a documentation system for built heritage at urban scale based on a CityGML data model. The main use case which motivates the development introduced in this section is the historic city of Segovia in Spain which contains a large amount of historic buildings, monuments and other cultural assets. In fact, cultural tourism is one of the main revenues of Segovia and they lack of technologies to improve the management and enhance the value of its cultural heritage. Thus, there are two different kinds of target user and, as a consequence, two different kinds of applications from two points of view: there is a need of tools to manage cultural heritage but there is also a need of tools to market cultural assets in tourism sector. Since both tools are fed by the same information, a common data model for city information is required which can be shared in real time by different users. More details about the concrete needs of these users are provided in Section 5.1

The rest of the section is divided as follows. Firstly, end user requirements are presented distinguishing two complementary tools. Then, the architecture of the system is described where the following subsections are defined: data storage backend, web services and end user applications. The first one details the developments performed to store information represented in CityGML (extensions and database). The second one describes the Web Services implemented for retrieving data. Finally, the last one advances implementation details of the user applications.

5.1 End User Requirements

The following section details the main requirements of user applications (the urban management tool and the application for the citizen) which motivate the implementation of the solution given below. Both applications access to the same stored data using web services.

The main goal of these applications is an efficient visualization of the geometric information of CityGML. Thus, some requirements for the solution are mandatory: a) progressive visualization is required such that instead of exporting the whole model, just the necessary objects are exported; b) taking into account the zoom level of the scene different LoDs of the model are visualized, it is also possible to show different LoD at the same time allowing to keep the attention of the end-user in a single building/set of buildings; c) users can select which different thematic layers are visualized according to their needs; d) the visualized geometry can be filtered with certain parameters from CityGML semantics; e) a bounding box can be selected in the viewer to spatially filter the visualized CityGML objects.

Urban Management Tool

This tool is intended for the agents responsible of the management and preservation of historic heritage in charge of maintaining and updating the data model. These agents need tools for helping them in decision making processes taking into account the peculiarities of historic urban environments from a territorial scale. The tool must be

able to navigate the model, to select different thematic layers of information, levels of detail and 3D objects. It will be deployed as a desktop application and it includes the ability to view and manage the set of attributes of the selected objects in the 3D viewer. The tool also allows semantic searches to filter city objects by a set of parameters. After, these objects will be highlighted using a different colour.

Application for the Citizen

This application is intended for citizens or visitors to the city area so it will be developed as a web application supporting multiple devices. It visualizes the information about the 3D model of the city and it queries the semantic information of CityGML in a mobile device. This tool retrieves the value of the attributes of the building by selecting the building in the 3D viewer. It allows selecting different layers to show different thematic information.

5.2 Architecture

The architecture has been developed taking into account the following features: flexibility, reusability and scalability. Furthermore, the logic and workflow is distributed between several computers such that information can be accessed and shared by different agents using open standards. Fig. 4 shows the three-layer designed architecture where presentation, business logic and data storage are distributed. The first one will be implemented on the client side, the second one will be shared between the client side and server side, and the third one will be on the server side. Communications will take place through standard OGC web services.

Figure 4: Overview of the system architecture [27]

5.3 Data storage

Extensions

As it was explained in Section 4, CityGML is a generic city object model which can be extended by ADEs. Thus, since CityGML do not represent well the documentation requirements in the fields of architectural and historical heritage, energy efficiency parameters and interventions in buildings, we have designed and developed three custom ADEs whose UML diagrams are represented by Figs. 5-7. The Cultural Heritage ADE models information such as monuments and sites by their name, location, functional type, date, history, physical condition and protection status. The Energy Efficiency ADE represents information about physical properties of materials such as conductivity, reflectivity, emissivity, transmittance, etc. Finally, the Intervention ADE allows representing what organization and actors are involved in the intervention processes to accomplish the maintenance and the rehabilitation of the cultural heritage city objects. With these three extensions it is possible to document our needs on these areas. Figs. 5-7 show the relationships between these new concepts and with CityGML classes [27].

Figure 5: Cultural Heritage Extension for CityGML

Figure 6: Energy Efficiency Extension for CityGML

Figure 7: Intervention Extension for CityGML

Storage

CityGML is intended to represent the semantic and geometric information of city objects. XML is the recommended format to exchange this information but it is not suitable for storing and retrieving complex city models where hundreds or thousands of objects can be involved. These files can take up to several gigabytes. Some other drawbacks of using XML are that redundant information is stored unnecessarily, data is more difficult to access and manage, there is no atomicity and integrity and the security level is lower. The alternative is to store the same information in a relational database system extended with spatial capabilities.

Dollner et al. [28] explain the new policy that has begun in Germany to create 3D models of cities. They developed a complex database scheme called 3D City Database [29] to represent and store the same information modeled by CityGML. This database has been complemented with an Importer/Exporter tool whose main objective is to process, store and retrieve efficiently and quickly CityGML dataset. More details about the import and export processes can be found in [30, 31]. One of the most recent improvements in this tool is the export to Collada and KML [31, 32]. The main drawback of this approach is the use of Oracle Spatial which is a proprietary and close-source relational database management system. Alternatively, we have developed and adapted the original database scheme to a PostgreSQL database extended by PostGIS [33]. However, the importer/exporter of 3D City Database does not work properly with PostgreSQL so we have also patched the original source code of the importer tool in order to work over a PostgreSQL database.

In order to support the storage of ADEs information mentioned above, we have designed and developed the necessary database scheme extensions which include a set of new tables, constraints and indices. We have also modified the importer/exporter tool to adapt it with our new extensions. Thus, we have achieved the inclusion of the CityGML data model together with its extensions stored in PostgreSQL database and the tool ready to import/export CityGML files to the underlying database.

5.4 Web Services

The access to the stored city objects is made through Web Services since it allows retrieving particular pieces of the whole city model and different stakeholders or applications share the same information. Thus, city models taking up to various gigabytes can be accessed and shared in real time.

Since one of our objectives is to improve interoperability, instead of creating new web services interfaces we have taken the standard Web service interfaces defined by the OGC such as the W3DS (Web 3D Service) and the WFS (Web Feature Service). W3DS allows retrieving geometric information and the second one the semantics.

W3DS

The W3DS (Web 3D Service) [34] allows to retrieve the geometry and appearance of three-dimensional models for visualization. It is still in draft phase as a previous step to final approval by the OGC. There is a reference implementation developed in OSM3D-Germany project [35] which implements almost all features of the standard specification. However, the software has not been open sourced, so we have developed our own implementation.

The W3DS accesses to the stored information and returns a KML or X3D file [34]. The client is responsible for rendering the model in contrast to the Web Feature Service where client has to generate the scene graph or the Web Perspective View Service where the server sends rendered images to the client.

Our implementation only serves the *GetScene* requests using parameters such as *Service*, *Request*, *Version*, *Format*, *BoundingBox*, *Layers* and *LoD*. Only *Service*, *Request*, *Version* and *Format* have always a fixed value while *BoundingBox*, *LoD* and

Layers parameters can be changed. By the moment, our implementation of *GetScene* request only includes the features required by our end user applications.

The request is done using a REST style call. REST is a philosophy of design for Web Services which tries to mimic the HTTP primitives to manipulate remotely allocated resources. GET retrieve a resource, POST creates a new resource, PUT modify or update a resource and DELETE remove the resource. The main advantage of REST is that it is based on open Web standards such as URI to represent the resources, HTTP to provide access to resources, and XML, HTML, etc. Finally, requests are done by means of a well-formed URL (Uniform Resource Locator).

GetScene request involves performing the following steps in the server side:

1. The ID of the building within the bounding box is retrieved. Fig. 8 represents the requested bounding box (P) and the building bounding box (Q). The following conditions must be met when a building is within the bounding box: $P_1 < Q_1$, $P_2(x) > Q_2(x)$ and $P_2(y, z) < Q_2(y, z)$, $P_3 > Q_3$, $P_4(x) < Q_4(x)$ and $P_4(y, z) > Q_4(y, z)$, $P_5 = Q_5$ and $Q_1 = Q_5$
2. A query statement is generated for each building, layer and LoD to achieve a more efficient visualization and selection of layers. Several files will be created for each layer and LoD of a building. These layers are the next ones: Wall Surface, Ground Surface, Closure Surface, Roof Surface, Interior Wall Surface and Ceiling Surface.
3. A SQL query is run against the database.
4. The cache of X3D files is queried such that if the file already exists it is not generated again by exporting from CityGML to X3D.
5. A main X3D file is generated with an *Inline* element for each one of the previously generated X3D files.
6. The files are streamed to the client.

WFS

WFS allow exchanging, sharing and managing georeferenced information between different agents. There exists several implementations of this service such as GeoServer project [36], which allow to publish geographic data developing an adapter that allow communicate with the database. Another alternative is the Deegree3 [37] environment which is more simple and flexible and offers an implementation of other OGC Web Services. We have selected Deegree3 because it can be easily integrated with PostGIS too. This service allows getting and modifying the semantic information of the CityGML model such that we can separate the access to the geometry (W3DS) and semantics (WFS). Communication with the service (requests and responses) is done via XML files according to the XML schema specifications of the OGC.

Figure 8: Bounding boxes used in W3DS implementation

5.4 End User Applications

Urban Management Tool

3D visualization is an important part of the interface of this tool which allows the user to navigate the model and picking individual objects. The tool retrieves the level of detail of 3D models according to the zoom level selected by the user using W3DS and X3D format. Xj3D [38] graphics engine has been used to develop the 3D viewer.

The selection of different layers is done manipulating *Inline* element in the main X3D file. Semantic searches and retrieval of building attributes are performed through the WFS. There are two ways of visualizing these attributes by selecting the building in the list or selecting the building in the 3D viewer. Fig. 9 shows a screenshot of the urban management tool running.

Figure 9: Screenshot of the Urban Management Tool

Application for the Citizen

Fig. 10 shows the methodology to visualize the 3D model. Geometries are retrieved through W3DS and exported to X3D which is visualized in a web browser without plugin using the X3DOM framework.

The 3D viewer allows the navigation of the model and the selection of the heritage buildings, parking, etc. which have been defined by the heritage manager previously. The rendering and the interaction with model components are implemented using X3DOM. This application uses the strategies about object attributes, levels of detail and layer visibility which was shown for the Urban Management Tool.

The use of a web browser without plugins allows citizens to perform visual and textual queries or navigate the 3D model (see Fig. 11) by means of a mobile device with traditional features such as GPS, network access and gyroscope.

Figure 10: Methodology for visualizing the geometry of CityGML [26]

Figure 11: Screenshot of the application for the citizens

6 Conclusions

This paper introduces an implementation of an efficient solution for visualization of the geometric information of CityGML. Our proposal improves performance in terms of file size and rendering time, using X3D for the representation of geometric information. In terms of file size, the X3D file represents almost a third of the size of the original model in CityGML. In terms of rendering time, the file structure and the way of representing the geometric primitives make X3D faster than CityGML. At the same time, a city model can be accessed via web by components, using the lower level of detail on large areas (urban level) and the higher level of detail in small regions (building level). The information is retrieved via W3DS and WFS, which guarantees interoperability with other implementations. Furthermore, only a web

browser is necessary to render the model which facilitates the access to information from any device (PC, tablets and smartphones). However, 3D Web visualization still presents some limitations in performance regarding the size of models and speed of rendering which are more noticeable in mobile devices with a low bandwidth.

The use of an extended CityGML data model enables the development of a documentation system for the built heritage based on a common and shared model. The information is accessible in a standard way through web services defined by the OGC, allowing management and access to information shared by different users.

Future developments include new navigation functionalities with different camera perspectives and walking modes, as well as the enhancement of interaction capabilities by triggering animations of CityGML objects with semantic information.

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